

Language as a Mirror of Culture: Exploring the Relationship between Language and Worldviews

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Abstract: the article examines the relationship between language and culture, methods of communication, language categories and worldview; how language reflects the uniqueness of culture and shapes thinking; analyzes transformations from different cultural and linguistic contexts to show how lexical, grammatical and stylistic features of language constitute a complex and unique background of perception through which native speakers comprehend and interpret the world around them.

Keywords: language, intercultural communication, cognitive processes, traditions and customs, vocabulary, culture, interrelationships.

Language is not just a means of communication between people. It is an important element of our culture and reflects the versatility of our thinking, traditions and customs; an important tool through which we perceive and interpret the world. As V. Dahl said: "Language is the age-old labor of a whole generation". From the point of view of linguistics, each language carries cultural codes, values and ideas about reality, peculiar to the speakers of this language.

One of the most famous examples of the relationship between language and world perception is the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis or linguistic relativity. The linguistic relativity hypothesis assumes that the structure of language affects the worldview and outlook of its speakers, as well as their cognitive processes.

The idea of the connection between language and thought goes back to the time of ancient civilizations. Plato's famous arguments against sophists such as Gorgias, who believed that the physical world could not be known in any way other than through language. Plato, on the other hand, believed that the world was made up of immanent eternal ideas, and that language, to be true, should try to reflect these ideas as accurately as possible. But others, such as Roger Bacon, believed that language was nothing more than a veil hiding eternal truths from actual human perception. For Immanuel Kant, language was just one of several tools by which humans know the world.

As is known, the lexicon of each language consists of two large layers: common vocabulary (understood by all speakers of this language, also known as literary language) and special vocabulary, in which we can distinguish: professional terminological vocabulary, which is used to describe activities, working situations and phenomena in a particular professional sphere, socially limited vocabulary: jargon vocabulary (argot and slang), territorial dialect words, or dialectisms obsolete words, etc.

But, the lexical composition of a language can also serve as an indicator of cultural priorities. For example, some languages, such as Russian, have special forms for types of action (perfect and imperfect), which may influence how speakers of these languages understand the concept of time and action; calling everyone “you” regardless of age is a statement of respect in Uzbek; Eskimos have many words for snow and ice, reflecting their attention to the environment and the need to distinguish between different types of snow depending on conditions. At the same time, in languages speaking about warmer climatic conditions, the number of words to describe snow is much smaller. This indicates different cultural emphases and what is important to the speakers.

In addition to vocabulary, it is worth noting the ways of communication, which differ from culture to culture. The issues of intercultural communication nowadays become especially important, as the interaction of representatives of different cultures in business, political and social contexts is an integral part of the modern world in the era of globalization. Since English has become a universal language of communication for representatives of different cultures, the issues of business intercultural communication effectiveness attract the attention of numerous researchers. If the norms of speech communication existing in one or another culture differ, we should assume that the communicative behavior of representatives of different cultures in similar situations will differ. This means that the communicative strategies, verbal and non-verbal means used by different cultures often do not match. Some languages, such as Japanese, have a system of politeness levels, indicating the importance of social hierarchies in Japanese society. Speakers learn to choose the appropriate forms of address depending on the status of the interlocutor, which emphasizes cultural norms and values regarding respect and hierarchy.

Language also plays an important role in the formation and expression of identity. For many people, their mother tongue becomes an integral part of their sense of self. In a situation of globalization, where languages and cultures intersect, the maintenance of the mother tongue becomes an important issue for the preservation of cultural identity. For example, various movements for the preservation of indigenous languages emphasize that language is not just a tool but also a carrier of a unique cultural heritage.

The study of the relationship between language and culture opens up many interesting perspectives for linguists, culturologists and researchers dealing with the issues of intercultural communication. Language, being a kind of mirror of culture, allows us to understand more deeply how native speakers perceive the surrounding world, themselves and their role in society. Understanding this principle of interrelationship enriches not only the knowledge of language as rules and traditions of a structured system, but also broadens our understanding of humanity in its cultural and social diversity. Research in this area exposes us to the diverse ways in which people living in different cultural contexts perceive the world.

Literature

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